

Scoring Tear Staining in Pigs: Similarity, Consistency, Accuracy, and Level of Experience.

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Tear stains, porphyrin-based marks secreted by the Harderian gland, appear around the inner corner and below the pig's eye. Tear stains have been historically linked to atrophic rhinitis and poor barn conditions. Still, tear staining has recently been proposed as a potential welfare indicator in pigs, particularly related to (social) stressors. This study aimed to evaluate whether tear stains in pigs can be reliably and accurately scored by naïve raters.

An inter- and intra-observer reliability study was conducted with 18 raters of varying experience in pig welfare assessment. Participants scored the tear stains under the left and right eye of 38 pigs (26 unique pigs and 12 repeats; 76 scores in total) using a tagged Visual Analog Scale (tVAS, continuous 0-100 scale) from short videos. Videos were collected from the slaughter line before scalding/dehairing and preselected by three trained experts to provide a "silver standard". The final 38 videos had scores ranging from 1 to 55 for left-eye stains and 1 to 63 for right-eye stains. Data was analyzed on the left and right data sets separately. Reliability was assessed using intra class correlation coefficients (ICC) for inter- and intra-rater aspects. Accuracy was estimated by linear mixed-effect modeling. Lastly, the effect of familiarity with pig welfare and tVAS scoring, as well as time to complete the scoring, was evaluated for all three aspects.

Preliminary results are presented.

Inter-rater reliability (single-rating, absolute-measurement, two-way random effects ICC) was *poor to moderate* (Left ICC [95% CI]: 0.434 [0.304, 0.605]; Right ICC: 0.360 [0.241, 0.531]). *Whereas, intra-rater reliability* (two-way mixed effects ICC per rater) showed *moderate to good* reliability (Left average ICC: 0.754 [0.676, 0.832]; Right average ICC: 0.677 [0.595, 0.758]). Further exploration showed that greater familiarity, experience, or time spent on scoring was associated with potential higher inter- and intra-rater reliability for both.

Accuracy, assessed using mixed-effects modeling, showed *moderate to high agreement* with the Silver Standard (Left: $\beta=0.78 \pm 0.10$, $p<0.001$; Right: $\beta=0.60 \pm 0.09$, $p<0.001$). Familiarity with scoring welfare in pigs, tVAS experience, and scoring time did not have a significant effect on the model. Bias analysis (bias = Score – Silver standard score) showed that raters on average tended to overestimate scores (Left bias = 1.80 [SD = 16.44]; Right bias = 2.74 [SD = 17.78]), with overestimation for low scores and underestimation for high scores as seen in bias plots.

Tear stain scoring results show poor to moderate reliability and relatively good accuracy, with intra-rater reliability outperforming inter-rater reliability, indicating that raters scored more consistently with themselves than with others. This, together with biases in extreme values, suggests the need for more in-depth training of the raters to enhance its potential as a welfare indicator in pigs.